

SCAVENGER HUNT

The first letter of each of the 11 answers can be combined to a solution phrase.
Hand in your solution at the registration desk no later than 04:00 pm on
20. November 2025 to participate in a little tombola!

Hint: The clues can be found
only in or around the
Klemperer-Saal.

 The clues can be found
only in or around the
Open Science Lab.

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(Given name / Surname)

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